

E2.2 Architecture for DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace v1.0

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Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

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WP Leader	i2CAT
Main Editor	Adriana Fernández-Fernández (i2CAT)
Contributors	i2CAT
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List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
API	Application Programming Interface
DID	Decentralised Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
ID	Identifier
ML	Machine Learning
RAN	Radio Access Network
SC	Smart Contract
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SD	Smart Discovery
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLO	Service-Level Objective
TM Forum	Tele Management Forum
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable E2.2 Architecture for DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). The document provides a comprehensive exploration of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, a novel solution centered on establishing a dynamic marketplace for distributed and secure trading of telco assets anchored on DLT to foster collaboration in the evolving landscape of 6G networks. In this regard, fundamental benefits of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace are discussed aligned to address the sustainable, ubiquitous and trustworthiness needs of 6G. Delving into the architectural realm, the document details the methodology and framework governing the Marketplace's architecture, providing high-level specifications for its sub-components. On the operational side, it explores the resulting software platform, outlining design principles and operational workflows that govern the platform's seamless functioning. The 6GENABLERS Marketplace stands out as a transformative force within the decentralized landscape, poised to revolutionize multi-party collaboration in 6G environments. This deliverable serves as a foundational guide for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. It explores the technical intricacies of the Marketplace, unveiling its potential to reshape the technological landscape. By adhering to best practices and strategic planning, this architecture sets the groundwork for a new era of efficiency, transparency, and innovation in the telecommunications industry.

1 Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of telecommunications, the convergence of cutting-edge technologies has paved the way for innovative solutions. The 6GENABLERS-DLT project emerges at the forefront, dedicated to harnessing the power of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to revolutionize the telecommunications industry.

Central to this initiative, is the conception of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, an ingenious decentralized platform grounded in DLTs. This document, titled "Architecture for DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace," serves as a pivotal deliverable in outlining the foundational design that will underpin the project's transformative endeavors.

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace stands as an innovative response to the intricate challenges prevalent in the collaborative landscapes of dynamic Sixth Generation (6G) environments. In this realm, where operators and service providers continually seek third-party resources to meet contractual obligations, the 6GENABLERS-DLT project aims to pioneer a holistic solution. At its essence, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace serves as a collaborative nexus, uniting operators, resource providers, and service providers in a dynamic ecosystem.

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace functions as an enabler where participants can not only showcase but also discover and trade resources efficiently. Its diverse offerings encompass a spectrum of 6G network infrastructure elements, ranging from Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) and Radio Access Network (RAN) assets to edge and cloud infrastructure. This extensive variety caters to the evolving demands of 6G environments, prioritizing flexibility and scalability.

Unlike traditional platforms, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace redefines the conventional norms of centralization embracing decentralization as a foundational principle. By adopting a decentralized architecture, the system transcends the limitations of a single point of failure, thereby eliminating the reliance on a central operator. Multiple interconnected nodes or instances collaboratively form a distributed network, ushering in transparency, trust, redundancy, fault tolerance, and resilience. Likewise, this Marketplace operates within a permissioned environment, deliberately crafted to mitigate vulnerabilities and complexities associated with open trading systems.

Within this decentralized paradigm, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace emerges not just as a platform but as an enabler for stakeholders to collectively harness resources, ushering in the next wave of technological advancements. As this deliverable delves into the intricate technical facets and functionalities of the Marketplace, it unveils the transformative potential that promises to reshape multi-party collaboration in the dynamic tapestry of 6G environments.

As a foundational document, the "Architecture for DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace" not only sets the stage for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project but also serves as a guiding beacon for developers, architects, and stakeholders involved in its realization. Through adherence to best practices and meticulous planning, this architecture aims to propel the telecommunications industry into a new era of efficiency, transparency, and innovation.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

The present document corresponds to the initial architecture design of the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace proposed in the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. As such, this deliverable provides a comprehensive architectural framework for the initial implementation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It encapsulates the meticulous planning and design considerations essential for realizing the first version of use case scenarios and requirements identified through rigorous technological analysis. In summary, the document encompasses a detailed architectural description, the high-level reference architecture diagram, specifications detailing the functional blocks in play, and the definition of provided services. The architecture outlined herein adheres to industry's best practices, ensuring a robust and scalable foundation that aligns seamlessly with the project's objectives.

In correspondence with the aforementioned scope, the primary objectives of this document are as follows:

- **Define Comprehensive Architectural Framework:** Clearly articulate a comprehensive architectural framework that encompasses the initial implementation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This includes detailing the relationships, dependencies, and interactions among various components, providing a holistic view of the system.
- **Ensure Alignment with Use Case Scenarios and Requirements:** Align the proposed architecture with the identified use case scenarios and requirements derived from technological components analysis. This involves mapping the architectural design to the specific needs and objectives of the project, ensuring that the system is poised to address the challenges and opportunities identified for a telecommunications marketplace.
- **Facilitate Understanding through Visual Representation:** Enhance comprehension among stakeholders by providing a high-level reference architecture diagram. This visual representation serves as a communicative tool, offering a clear and concise overview of the system's structure, interactions, and key components. It aids stakeholders in understanding the project's architecture without delving into intricate technical details.
- **Enable Practical Implementation with Service Definitions:** Facilitate the practical implementation of the architecture by providing explicit definitions of services. This objective ensures that developers and system integrators have a clear understanding of the services offered by the architecture and how external entities can interact with them. Clear service definitions promote seamless integration and interoperability.

These objectives collectively aim to guide the development and implementation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, promoting clarity, alignment with project goals, and practicality in execution.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable stands as a significant achievement within Work Package 2 (P2), which is dedicated to offering an in-depth depiction of the DLT-anchored Marketplace platform. P2's overarching objective is to present a comprehensive understanding of the platform's

capabilities, demonstrated through technically oriented scenarios. Furthermore, the work package is committed to designing an architecture that not only meets the requirements of the project's enablers but also ensures adaptability during implementation. This design prioritizes crucial architectural qualities, including reliability, scalability, and maintainability. The ultimate aim is to establish a resilient and efficient framework that aligns seamlessly with the evolving demands of the envisioned 6G networks, capitalizing on the foundational capabilities of DLT as a transformative technology.

Figure 1-1. E2.2 positioning and relation to the project's activities

As depicted in Figure 1-1, deliverable E2.2 is the result of the work done in task A2.6 within P2, which is described below:

- A2.6 – DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace Architecture: This task focuses on producing the functional architecture for the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace. The proposed architecture shall encompass the needs and requirements at the business level, as well as the system level intricacies taking into account envisioned 6G systems characteristics. Moreover, a revised platform design will be also delivered in a subsequent deliverable (E2.3) taking into account the outcomes from the implementation results of P3, P4 and P5.

At the business level, A2.6 ensures alignment with the overarching goals and requirements, crafting an architecture that resonates with the strategic vision of the project. Simultaneously, the system level intricacies are meticulously considered, integrating characteristics intrinsic to envisioned 6G systems. These characteristics envision mobile telecommunications infrastructures that are not only flexible and provisioned on-demand but also capable of providing pervasive computing and connectivity across diverse domains. The system requirements and capabilities collected in previous tasks from the different technological pillars, as well as their initial components design, have played a crucial role in shaping the functional architecture of the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace, presented in this document. This comprehensive deliverable lays the groundwork for subsequent project phases, ensuring a robust approach to the architectural evolution of the system.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The structure of the current document is organized to provide a comprehensive exploration of the architecture design for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The document unfolds as follows:

- Section 1: This section provides an overview of the document, including its objectives, its relationship to project activities, and an outline of its internal structure.
- Section 2: Diving into the technological core, this section delves into the functional systems and services overview of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.
- Section 3: The architectural foundation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace takes center stage in this section. It unfolds the architectural design methodology and framework architecture, offering a detailed exposition of the high-level specifications of the sub-components that form the backbone of the platform.
- Section 4: Shifting the focus towards the operational aspects, this section zooms in on the software platform. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the platform's design rationale, guiding principles, platform overview and operational workflows that facilitate the seamless functioning of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.
- Section 5: The document culminates with a concluding section that synthesizes the main findings and encapsulates key takeaways.
- Section 6: The reference section serves as a repository of sources and citations that substantiate the information presented throughout the document.

2 DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace stands as a pioneering solution, purposefully designed to address sustainable and ubiquitous needs integral to the evolution of 6G environments. In an era where the demand for seamless collaboration intersects with the imperative for sustainability, this decentralized platform emerges as a strategic response to propel the telecommunications industry into a more environmentally conscious and widely accessible future.

By fostering a collaborative ecosystem that transcends traditional boundaries, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace aligns with the sustainability objectives inherent to 6G. Its decentralized architecture not only enhances reliability and fault tolerance but also inherently contributes to resource optimization and energy efficiency. By means of infrastructure sharing between multiple parties, the Marketplace promotes a sustainable model that resonates with the evolving landscape of next-generation networks.

Figure 2-1 illustrates the decentralized nature of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This is achieved by endowing each stakeholder with a marketplace instance, which is interconnected with the rest of participant instances through the DLT network. Using this network, the Marketplace participants are able to share softwarized network services and infrastructure components, providing ubiquitous computing and connectivity capabilities, which unlock the ability to furnish on-demand and pervasive service provisioning across domains.

Figure 2-1. Overview of the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace

Moreover, the permissioned nature of the Marketplace fosters a controlled and regulated environment, aligning with the privacy and security prerequisites crucial for the widespread adoption of 6G technologies. This deliberate approach ensures that the 6GENABLERS Marketplace not only meets the immediate collaborative needs of 6G environments but does so in a manner that is both environmentally responsible and universally accessible.

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace not only caters to the sustainable and ubiquitous needs of 6G but also places a paramount emphasis on trustworthiness, a critical aspect engendered by the utilization of DLT. As the telecommunications landscape evolves, the need for a trustworthy and transparent framework becomes increasingly imperative, and the 6GENABLERS Marketplace addresses this need with its innovative approach.

DLT serves as the bedrock of trust in the Marketplace, offering a decentralized ledger that records transactions across multiple nodes. This not only enhances transparency but also ensures the immutability of records, fostering a level of trust that is inherently resistant to tampering or unauthorized alterations. Participants within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace can transact with confidence, knowing that the integrity of the system is upheld through the robust and secure nature of DLT.

The permissioned environment, coupled with DLT, reinforces the trustworthiness of the Marketplace. Participants, authorized within this controlled ecosystem, can engage in collaborative endeavors with the assurance that their interactions are secure, verifiable, and traceable. This deliberate approach not only instills confidence among stakeholders but also mitigates the risks associated with open and unregulated trading systems.

In embracing decentralization as a core design principle, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace not only safeguards against single points of failure but also inherently enhances trust. The distributed nature of the network, facilitated by DLT, ensures that trust is not reliant on a central authority but is distributed across the interconnected nodes, creating a resilient and trustworthy foundation for collaboration.

In summary, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace emerges as a transformative solution that not only meets the sustainable, ubiquitous, and trustworthy needs of 6G but actively contributes to shaping a future telecommunications ecosystem characterized by environmental responsibility, inclusivity, and heightened levels of trust among its diverse stakeholders.

2.1 Functional Systems

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace is conceived as a multi-system platform underpinned by four core functional systems, represented in Figure 2-2, each playing a pivotal role in shaping the collaborative and innovative landscape of the framework.

Figure 2-2. Core functional systems of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace

These functional systems or technological pillars are designed to synergistically interact, providing a seamless and efficient environment for participants. Below, we delve into the key characteristics and contributions of each core functional system:

- At the heart of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace lies the DLT system. DLT serves as the foundational bedrock, ensuring transparent, secure, and decentralized record-keeping. It facilitates the creation of a shared ledger distributed across multiple nodes, fostering trust and immutability within the Marketplace. The DLT system forms the backbone of secure transactions and establishes a tamper-resistant environment, enhancing the overall reliability and integrity of the collaborative platform.
- Smart Contracts constitute an automated layer within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. These self-executing contracts encode and automate the negotiation, execution, and enforcement of agreements between participants. By embedding predefined business rules into the code, Smart Contracts streamline transactions, minimize the need for intermediaries, and enhance the efficiency of resource exchanges. This system ensures that contractual agreements are executed with precision, transparency, and reliability, fostering a trustful environment for collaborative engagements.
- The Smart Discovery system within the framework empowers participants to efficiently explore and engage with the diverse resources available in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Leveraging intelligent algorithms, this system enables stakeholders to identify relevant resources based on specific needs and preferences. Smart Discovery simplifies the searching of appealing offers and contributes to the agility of the Marketplace by facilitating dynamic and context-aware resource discovery.
- The SLA Assurance system is integral to ensuring that interactions within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace adhere to predefined service standards. This system automates the verification of compliance with SLAs in real-time, monitoring participant performance against agreed-upon benchmarks. By automating this critical aspect, the SLA Assurance system enhances trust among participants, fosters transparency, and establishes a basis for accountable collaborations within the Marketplace.

In concert, these core functional systems define the 6GENABLERS Marketplace framework, creating a dynamic and secure ecosystem where DLT, Smart Contracts, Smart Discovery, and SLA Assurance harmonize to meet the evolving demands of collaborative telecommunications environments.

2.2 Services Overview

The robust architecture of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is empowered by its core functional systems. By leveraging them, the resulting framework facilitates a suite of internal functionalities that are fundamental to its seamless operation. These internal functionalities are intricately woven into the fabric of the platform, ensuring efficient and secure performance. These internal functionalities, graphically illustrated in Figure 2-3, collectively form the heartbeat of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Next, we delve into each of these functionalities, exploring their significance and role in fostering a collaborative and innovative telecommunications landscape.

Figure 2-3. Overview of functionalities provided by the 6GENABLERS Marketplace

A. Management of Distributed Identities

In the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, the robust management of distributed identities is a fundamental service that ensures secure and seamless participation of stakeholders. This functionality encompasses the creation, validation, and maintenance of decentralized identities for participants within the network. Leveraging DLT, each entity in the ecosystem possesses a unique and verifiable identity, fostering a trustworthy environment where interactions are attributed to authenticated participants. This identity management system enhances security, reduces the risk of unauthorized access, and facilitates traceability within the collaborative marketplace.

B. Secure and Untampered Data Propagation Cross-Domains

Enabled by the inherent security features of the DLT system, this functionality ensures the integrity and confidentiality of data (related to offerings, orders, etc.) as it traverses the decentralized network, fostering a reliable and resilient information propagation mechanism. Each participant node contributes to the security and resilience of the data, preventing unauthorized alterations and preserving the integrity of the unbroken chain. The decentralized nature of the platform ensures that data is distributed across multiple nodes, reducing vulnerabilities associated with centralized systems and enhancing overall security.

C. Automatic Transactions Ruled by Smart Contracts

The Marketplace facilitates automatic transactions governed by smart contracts, a revolutionary capability that streamlines and enforces predefined agreements between parties. Smart contracts, executed on the decentralized platform, automate the negotiation, execution, and enforcement of contractual terms. This not only expedites the transaction process but also ensures precision and transparency. By embedding business rules directly into the code, the Marketplace mitigates the need for intermediaries, reduces the risk of disputes, and enhances the efficiency of resource exchange among participants.

D. Smart Classification of Offers and Intent-Based Discovery

Smart discovery is a key functionality that empowers participants to efficiently explore, evaluate, and engage with the diverse array of resources available within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Leveraging intelligent algorithms and the decentralized nature of the platform, smart discovery enables stakeholders to identify relevant resources based on their specific needs and preferences. This internal capability enhances the platform's efficiency by classifying offers intelligently and facilitating intent-based discovery. Participants benefit from a dynamic and context-aware environment that facilitates interaction with the platform and encourages collaborative engagements.

E. Verification of Compliance with SLA

Ensuring adherence to SLAs is a critical functionality provided by the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Through automated verification mechanisms, the platform monitors and assesses the performance of participants in real-time against predefined SLAs. This service guarantees that contractual obligations are met, and the quality of services remains consistent. Automated SLA verification not only enhances trust among participants but also provides a basis for transparent and accountable collaborations within the marketplace.

Building on the aforementioned capabilities, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace extends a suite of services to its stakeholders, fostering seamless interaction, collaboration, and resource exchange within the platform. These services represent the external face of the platform, empowering stakeholders to create, discover, and engage with offerings in a dynamic and responsive ecosystem. The diverse services exposed by the 6GENABLERS Marketplace are outlined next, showcasing how stakeholders can leverage the platform's capabilities to meet their unique needs and drive innovation in the ever-evolving landscape of telecommunications.

1. **Creation of Offers:** Stakeholders can leverage the platform to create, and showcase offers, outlining the resources or services they are willing to provide within the collaborative ecosystem. This service streamlines the process of presenting offerings to potential consumers within the marketplace.

2. **Offers Discovery:** The Offers Discovery service enables participants to efficiently explore and discover relevant resources and services available within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Leveraging intelligent algorithms, this service ensures that stakeholders can easily identify and engage with offerings that align with their specific needs.

3. **Placement of Orders:** Stakeholders can initiate the creation of orders, specifying their selection of resources or services offered within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This service streamlines the process of formalizing collaborative engagements and resource transactions.

4. **Deployment of Orders:** After acquiring some resources offered, this service ensures the efficient execution and fulfillment of orders within the marketplace. Participants can deploy the specified resources or services, fostering a seamless and automated process that aligns with the predefined terms and conditions outlined in smart contracts.

5. **Tracking of SLA Compliance:** The Tracking of SLA Compliance service empowers stakeholders to monitor and track the adherence of transactions and engagements to

predefined SLAs. This ensures accountability, transparency, and a basis for trust within the collaborative framework of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

In essence, these internal functionalities and exposed services collectively form the backbone of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, creating a dynamic and collaborative environment that caters to the diverse needs of stakeholders within the telecommunications ecosystem. This comprehensive suite of functionalities and services underscores the platform's commitment to efficiency, security, and transparency in the collaborative landscape of 6G environments.

3 6GENABLERS Marketplace Architecture

This section delves into the 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture, offering a broad overview of the high-level specifications of the architectural framework. Emphasizing an iterative approach, periodic revisions of this framework will be integrated throughout the development stages spanning P3, P4 and P5.

To facilitate comprehension, the section commences with an introduction to the architectural design methodology, providing a methodical lens to understand the subsequent discussions. Subsequently, it provides a high-level perspective on the 6GENABLERS Marketplace framework, presenting an overarching view of the system. Following this, a detailed examination of each sub-component is offered, outlining their functions within the proposed framework. This journey through the architectural landscape of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace seeks to offer a neutral and informative exploration, where each component contributes systematically to the collaborative vision in the telecommunications realm.

3.1 Architectural Design Methodology

To formulate the architecture design of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, the considered methodology encompassed the following sequential steps, as elucidated in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1. High-level architectural design methodology

a) Pre-design, System Capabilities and Requirements:

The initiation point involved an exploration of the functional systems as technological pillars initially outlined in the project proposal. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis of relevant work, use case scenarios and systems capabilities and requirements (reported in deliverable E2.1 [1]) contributed to shaping the foundation for the subsequent design phases.

b) System Level Design of Components:

Each partner engaged in the project contributed to the system-level design of individual sub-components within each functional system (reported in deliverables E3.1 [2], E4.1

[3] and E5.1 [4]). Key elements addressed encompassed a generic description outlining overall operation and computational aspects, high-level functional schemes, the identification of key technologies, detailed sub-component descriptions, interface specifications among sub-components and with other 6GENABLERS Marketplace components, and a summary of expected operational flows.

c) High-level Architecture Design:

The current phase is centered on synthesizing the individual component designs into the high-level architecture for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace (being reported in deliverable E2.2). This entailed a domain-level design addressing the overarching architecture, where the proposed designs of individual components were amalgamated to create a cohesive and integrated framework.

d) Platform Prototype Implementation:

Following the high-level design, the project transitions into the implementation phase (to be reported in deliverables E3.2, E4.2 and E5.2), where the platform prototype will be developed based on the aggregated designs. This stage involves the practical instantiation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, providing a tangible representation of the architecture envisioned.

e) High-level Architecture and Components Refinement:

The final stage encompasses the refinement of both the high-level architecture (to be reported in deliverable E2.3) and individual components (to be reported in deliverables E3.3, E4.3 and E5.3). This refinement will allow for iterative improvements and adjustments to enhance the adaptability, efficiency, and effectiveness of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture.

In summary, the considered methodology employs systematic progression through pre-design, system-level and high-level design, prototype implementation, and refinement phases to meticulously craft the architecture for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, aligning it with the project's objectives and the dynamic landscape of 6G telecommunications environments.

3.2 Framework Architecture

The high-level reference architecture of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is depicted in Figure 3-2, serving as a foundational blueprint for the platform's dynamic operation. From a functional point of view, this architecture is split vertically across two distinct layers, namely the Business Layer and the Monitoring and Control Layer, and is positioned on top of the Network Infrastructure. Each functional layer encapsulates diverse functionalities, adhering to a service-centric architectural model.

- **Business Layer:** Dedicated to trading management, the Business Layer plays a pivotal role in orchestrating the collaborative exchange within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This stratum encompasses the management of identities, facilitating secure and seamless participation, alongside the dynamic generation of offers, orders, and Smart Contract (SC) states as novel components that track updates related to the telco assets post-acquisition. Here, the essence lies in fostering a transparent and efficient trading environment, where identities are

managed with integrity, and the lifecycle of traded resources is meticulously tracked and updated.

- **Monitoring and Control Layer:** The core of enforcement lies within the Monitoring and Control Layer, where ordered items are seamlessly managed. This layer is instrumental in the orchestration of infrastructure resources, facilitating the instantiation of softwarized assets, and rigorously tracking SLAs. It is the operational nerve that ensures the ordered components are not only deployed but also adhere to the predefined agreements. This layer embodies precision, efficiency, and real-time control, ensuring the deployment and post-deployment monitoring actions of collaborative transactions within the Marketplace.
- **Network Infrastructure:** While external to the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, the Network Infrastructure is a linchpin in the conceptualization of the framework architecture. This stratum hosts not only the resources subject to trading but the orchestration and management entities, along with monitoring exporters. These entities are integrated with the components of the Monitoring and Control Layer, creating a symbiotic relationship that ensures tight integration. The Network Infrastructure forms the backbone that supports and sustains the operational dynamics of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, providing the necessary infrastructure for seamless collaboration and resource exchange.

Figure 3-2. 6GENABLERS Marketplace high-level architecture

It is imperative to emphasize that the two strata of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace Architecture, i.e., Business Layer and Monitoring and Control Layer, intricately encapsulate the pivotal pillars of the 6ENABLERS-DLT project. These include the four foundational functional systems outlined previously in Section 2.1, namely: DLT, governing secure and transparent participation; Smart Contracts, orchestrating automated and rule-based transactions; Smart Discovery, facilitating collaborative engagement; and SLA Assurance, ensuring adherence to predefined agreements.

Figure 3-2 shows a single-domain instance of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. As explained in the previous section, this instance is replicated in every stakeholder domain. Regarding interaction, sub-components belonging to the same stakeholder interact with each other through direct Application Programming Interface (API) calls or through the Data Bus, which bridges the two functional layers allowing asynchronous exchange between multiple sub-components. Meanwhile, the propagation of information between the different providers is conducted through the two considered DLT networks (Trading DLT and Identity DLT). Connectivity between sub-components is represented and detailed in Section 4 to better illustrate the software platform featuring the proposed architectural framework.

A more detailed description of the roles and functionalities of each sub-component is provided in the subsequent subsection.

3.2.1 High-level Specification of Sub-Components

This section delineates the pivotal sub-components that constitute the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, derived from the comprehensive breakdown of the overall reference architecture. Each sub-component plays a unique role, contributing to the seamless orchestration of transactions, management of identities, and enforcement of critical aspects like resource/service deployment and SLA compliance. It's important to note that not all these entities are directly exposed to 6GENABLERS users. In fact, certain entities remain internal, playing a crucial role in supporting the operation of the Marketplace.

3.2.1.1 Trading DLT and Identity DLT

As a fundamental pillar supporting the Business Layer of the considered architecture, we encounter the DLT. Specifically, in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace two blockchains are considered to deal with the management of transactions and identities indistinctively. The reason for this decision is the presence of state-of-the-art technologies specialized in each one of these two aspects.

The Trading DLT serves as the backbone of the Marketplace, providing a repository for data related to offers, orders, and SC states. It operates as a distributed database, ensuring real-time distribution and synchronization of data across all DLT nodes. That is, when an operation is committed to the ledger, it is distributed through the network, so that all the DLT nodes have the same information at the same time. Implemented through Hyperledger Fabric [5], this decentralized ledger guarantees transparency and simultaneity in transactional data dissemination.

Grounded in decentralized identity principles, the Identity DLT removes the need of relying on a central authority or identity provider. This component ensures privacy, authenticity, and security in the creation and maintenance of decentralized digital

identities within the Marketplace, by storing identifiers (IDs) and credentials on the ledger. For the implementation of this DLT, the Hyperledger Indy [6] has been chosen as blockchain framework specifically designed for decentralized identity management.

Additional specifications of these modules, such as deployment aspects, are further detailed in deliverable E3.1 [2].

3.2.1.2 Identity Manager API

In a permissioned and distributed environment, privacy and authentication are non-negotiable. The Identity Manager API acts as a controlled interface, ensuring that only authorized requests for identity-related actions are processed. By channeling all identity-related operations through the Identity Manager API, the system upholds a strict governance model, safeguarding the privacy and authenticity of participants.

The Identity Manager API module ensures end-to-end identity management processes. It's responsible for issuing, validating, and revoking identities within the Marketplace, utilizing Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) for enhanced privacy, authenticity, and security. In a distributed environment spanning multiple administrative domains, the Identity Manager API is instrumental in generating DIDs not only for participants but also for other entities like offers, orders, and SC states.

This cross-domain identifier sharing is crucial for seamless collaboration and resource identification across diverse entities within the Marketplace. This module plays a pivotal role in managing identities throughout the Identity DLT network, acting as unique entry-point for interacting with this blockchain. This centralized entry-point guarantees the integrity of DIDs, promoting trust and accountability within the Marketplace. In addition to identifying the stakeholders, DIDs will be also generated to identify other entities to be shared cross-domains such as offers, orders and SC states.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E3.1 [2].

3.2.1.3 Offering API, Order API and SC State API

Internal to the Business Layer, a set of three APIs are made available to allow the interaction with the Trading DLT. Their roles are based on the three main entities handled in the Marketplace for transaction establishment, namely: i) offers, which provides the description of supplied resources to be traded including their technical characteristics, price, and SLA; ii) orders, which contains the demand for acquiring a published offer over a given period of time; and iii) SC states, which represents the deployment request to activate the acquired resources and are used to track all the post-acquisition events associated to the traded asset. These APIs, also referred as DLT APIs, forward to the Trading DLT the input information that triggers the execution of the smart contract coded in the ledger for the Marketplace operations.

The Offering API is a vital component for managing the lifecycle of offers within the Trading DLT. It includes functionalities for retrieving existing offers, creating new offers, updating offers, and cancelling active offers. This API ensures a dynamic and responsive trading environment, empowering participants to interact seamlessly. Given the nature of blockchain structures, the cancellation of an active offer implies changing its status to

‘cancelled’, although the record of the offer remains in the Trading DLT and can still be revised.

Similarly, the Order API is dedicated to managing the lifecycle of orders within the Trading DLT. Its functionalities cover the retrieval of existing orders, addition of new orders, updating orders, and cancelling active orders. The Order API contributes to the efficient and streamlined execution of transactions, enhancing the overall trading experience, and ensuring a dynamic and responsive market environment.

The SC State API is dedicated to facilitating the recording and management of SC states. This API will be used to trigger the deployment of acquired resources and their post-purchase follow-up. Consequently, this component plays a crucial role in providing dynamic updates to the Trading DLT by recording changes on the ledger related to the deployment and SLA compliance statuses.

Additional specifications of these modules, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E3.1 [2].

3.2.1.4 Smart Contract State Composer

The Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC) assumes a central role within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, acting as the nexus between the invoking stakeholder and the DLT APIs for seamless interaction within the Marketplace.

The SCSC facilitates to users, through programmable means, the submission of new resource and service offerings, the visualization of available offers from other domains, the placement of orders, and the request for resource deployment, enhancing the interactive capabilities with the Marketplace. To achieve this, it works in collaboration with the SC Codes that are committed to the Trading DLT in the form of ChainCodes. Additionally, the SCSC remains sensitive to alarms and events, ensuring stakeholders are promptly notified of changes in asset availability and performance based on inputs for the Control and Monitoring Layer.

Beyond its role as an interaction facilitator, the SCSC is integral to the definition and validation of models within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Drawing from TMForum standards, it defines models that ensure trustworthiness and uniqueness of traded telco services. In the validation process, the SCSC plays a crucial role in ensuring instantiated orders align with agreed-upon transactions. It integrates with ChainCodes to insert offers, orders and SC states into the DLT, creating logical links between entities and incorporating verification methods, to maintain the integrity of traded assets and prevent post-transaction alterations.

As a transaction workflow manager, the SCSC guides stakeholders through CRUD operations for offers, orders, and SC states, serving as the single entry-point for stakeholder interactions with the DLT. Likewise, it responds to inputs and events from the Control and Monitoring Layer and forwards them for recording into the Trading DLT. This ensures logical links between objects and maintains the integrity of the Trading DLT records through systematic creation and updating.

Furthermore, the SCSC takes on the role of a document renderer, implementing a template rendering service for document creation. This functionality allows for the programmatic generation of human-readable SC report documents. By summarizing key

fields from the transaction's chain of models, the SCSC plays a crucial role in facilitating auditing processes.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E4.1 [3].

3.2.1.5 Smart Discovery Application

Designed to bring advanced functionalities to the Marketplace, the Smart Discovery Application automates the identification and curation of multi-party resources, fostering intelligent interaction with the platform. Its role is pivotal in ensuring participants can discover and engage with relevant resources efficiently, facilitating intelligent identification of available offers.

At the core of this intelligent resource discovery lies the integration of ML-based models. Central to this approach is the implementation of data clustering methodologies, which group resources based on identified common features. Then, through online predictions, incoming offers are classified into established clusters, establishing the groundwork for the identification process during the discovery phase. Using these sophisticated techniques, the application aims to streamline the identification and acquisition of a tailored subset of network resources and services precisely aligned with the consumer's requirements and expectations.

One of the innovative features the Smart Discovery Application introduces is the automated, intent-based API invocation. This approach will significantly reduce the burden on stakeholders, eliminating the need for them to explicitly call the Offering API to obtain all the published offers and search through all of them the most suitable ones. Instead, the the Smart Discovery Application will intelligently discern the users' intent and automatically invoke the Offering API to retrieve a filtered subset of offers aligned to the users' need.

The intent-based API simplifies the offer exploration process, allowing users to declare their intentions abstractly, as opposed to meticulously detailing attributes through intricate filters. This declarative approach aligns with user intentions, prescribing the type of resource and prioritizing specific aspects. In essence, the module deciphers keywords within the provided intention, translating them into the most appealing cluster of offers.

The Smart Discovery application, with its blend of intent-driven assistance and ML-powered insights, emerges as a cornerstone in revolutionizing how stakeholders interact with and explore the diverse array of offerings within the dynamic landscape of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E5.1 [4].

3.2.1.6 Data Bus

The Data Bus within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace serves as a critical communication fabric, playing a pivotal role in fostering seamless interaction and integration among various sub-components of both the Monitoring and Control Layer and the Business Layer. Its unique design enables the adoption of an event-driven paradigm, facilitating

dynamic and real-time communication that is instrumental for the overall functionality and coordination of the Marketplace.

One of the key functionalities of the Data Bus is to act as a centralized communication hub for the components within the Monitoring and Control Layer. By adopting an event-driven approach, the Data Bus enables efficient and timely exchange of information between different entities, such as the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator, the Broker Logic for Resource Controller, and the Proactive SLA Monitoring. This event-driven paradigm ensures that relevant data and events are disseminated instantly across the layer, allowing for coordinated responses and actions based on the real-time state of the network.

Moreover, the Data Bus serves as a crucial integration point between the Monitoring and Control Layer and the Business Layer. As the DLT APIs write to the Data Bus, they provide a mechanism for updating and sharing transactional information, related to for instance the publication of new objects to the DLT or the DID assignment, with the broader ecosystem. This integration is particularly vital for the SCSC, which reads updates from the Data Bus. This interaction enables the SCSC to stay synchronized with the latest changes and transactions in the DLT as well as events coming from the Network Infrastructure, ensuring that it can effectively manage the lifecycle of smart contracts and associated resources.

In essence, the Data Bus serves as a unifying communication infrastructure that facilitates coordination and information exchange across different layers of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture. The event-driven paradigm not only enhances the responsiveness of the Monitoring and Control Layer but also ensures seamless and near-real-time integration with the Business Layer, contributing to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the marketplace operations.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E5.1 [4].

3.2.1.7 Broker Logic for Resource Controller

The Broker Logic for Resource Controller assumes a critical role in the Monitoring and Control Layer. This module is at the forefront of resource deployment, listening to the Data Bus for resource deployment requests, checking availability, and orchestrating deployment announcements, ensuring a responsive and efficient integration with the Network Infrastructure. Its pivotal role can be justified through various key aspects that contribute to the overall functionality and success of the Marketplace ecosystem.

Firstly, the resource deployment orchestration is a fundamental responsibility of the Broker Logic for Resource Controller. Positioned as a central orchestration point, it manages actions related to the deployment of resources based on specifications contained in the smart contracts. By serving as an intermediary between the Marketplace platform and the Network Infrastructure, it guarantees that deployment actions align precisely with the contractual agreements.

Secondly, the Broker Logic for Resource Controller facilitates seamless communication with network controllers. This communication is essential for verifying the availability of resources and initiating the deployment process. Through coordination with network controllers, the Broker ensures that the offered and requested resources are compatible

with the current state of the network, contributing to the accuracy and effectiveness of resource allocation.

Finally, real-time updates on the status of resource deployment constitute another significant contribution of the Broker Logic for Resource Controller. By interfacing with the Data Bus, it publishes information about ongoing deployments, enabling stakeholders and other components within the architecture (such as the SCSC, the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator and the Proactive SLA Monitoring) to stay informed about the progress and completion of resource instantiation.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E5.1 [4].

3.2.1.8 Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator

The Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator contributes to the SLA assurance loop within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture. Its significance lies in its capacity to serve as a central hub for the comprehensive collection and aggregation of network metrics. By capturing data from diverse segments of the infrastructure, the Aggregator ensures a holistic perspective on the network's performance, spanning various infrastructure segments.

The Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator's role consists of collecting network metrics, acting as the initial point for data collection, gathering information on network performance. Real-time monitoring is a key feature facilitated by the Aggregator, setting the stage for the instantaneous detection of any deviations from predefined SLA metrics. This capability is crucial in ensuring that the network consistently meets the agreed-upon performance and allows for prompt responses to potential issues.

The Aggregator focuses on monitoring the corresponding metrics from SLA rules, which are read from the Data Bus. This step ensures alignment between network metrics and predefined SLA objectives, a critical aspect for assessing whether the actual network performance adheres to agreed-upon service levels.

One of the Aggregator's essential functions is the integration with the underlying Network Infrastructure. It seamlessly interfaces with monitoring exporters across different network segments to obtain the corresponding network metrics. Finally, the integration between the Aggregator and the Data Lake is fundamental, as it enables the storage of collected metrics in a time-series database.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E5.1 [4].

3.2.1.9 Data Lake

The Data Lake entity is responsible for registering and storing all the metrics collected by the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator. This centralized storage, in the form of a time series database, allows for efficient retrieval and analysis of network metrics.

First and foremost, the Data Lake serves as a centralized repository for the registration and storage of all the metrics collected from different segments of the network infrastructure. This storage capability ensures that a comprehensive and historical record of network performance metrics is readily available for analysis and evaluation. By

retaining this historical data, the Data Lake supports retrospective assessments of SLA compliance, enabling stakeholders to identify patterns, trends, and potential areas for improvement.

The integration of the Data Lake with the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator is foundational. The Aggregator, responsible for collecting network metrics, relies on the Data Lake for the persistent storage of this information in a time-series database. This integration enables the aggregation of metrics from diverse infrastructure segments, fostering a unified and standardized representation of network performance data.

Furthermore, the Data Lake plays a pivotal role in the transparency and accountability of SLA compliance. The stored metrics provide a basis for audit trails and reports, enabling stakeholders to trace and verify the performance of the network over time. This feature is particularly valuable in addressing compliance requirements, regulatory standards, and contractual obligations within the dynamic and collaborative environment of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E5.1 [4].

3.2.1.10 Proactive SLA Monitoring

The Proactive SLA Monitoring component within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture plays a pivotal role in ensuring the robustness and effectiveness of the SLA assurance loop. Its functions and capabilities contribute significantly to the real-time assessment and enforcement of SLAs, enhancing the overall reliability and quality of services within the dynamic and collaborative environment of the Marketplace.

At its core, Proactive SLA Monitoring is responsible for continuously checking and evaluating the network infrastructure metrics against the predefined SLA metrics, ensuring that the actual performance aligns with the agreed-upon service levels. This real-time monitoring enables the system to promptly identify any deviations or potential violations from the agreed-upon service levels. By actively corroborating the network performance metrics stored in the Data Lake, the Proactive SLA Monitoring component acts as an early-warning system, allowing stakeholders to take swift corrective actions in response to emerging issues or deviations.

One key aspect of the Proactive SLA Monitoring's role is its capacity to predict future SLA values. By analyzing historical performance data and trends stored in the Data Lake, the component can forecast the expected trajectory of SLA metrics. This predictive capability enhances the system's ability to proactively address potential SLA breaches before they occur, providing stakeholders with valuable insights into the trajectory of network performance.

Moreover, Proactive SLA Monitoring is integral to the responsiveness of the SLA assurance loop. In the event of an SLA violation or status change, the component communicates this information via the Data Bus to the broader system, alerting other relevant components to trigger necessary actions. This communication ensures a timely and coordinated response to maintain the integrity of the SLA commitments and uphold the quality of services within the Marketplace.

Additional specifications of this module, such as exposed service endpoints and example workflows, are further detailed in deliverable E5.1 [4].

4 Software Platform Overview

This section delves into the practical application of the principles elucidated in Section 3, providing a comprehensive overview of the overarching software design shaping the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. As we navigate through this exploration, we will witness how these principles, meticulously outlined earlier, have been translated into the tangible and cohesive software platform that underpins the dynamic functionalities of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

4.1 Platform Design Principles

The foundational concept guiding the software design of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace revolves around structuring the platform as a collection of modules as per the framework architecture defined in Section 3. In alignment with contemporary best practices, we adhere to a service-based pattern, where each module signifies a platform service, fostering modularity and ease of integration. These components are distinguished by several key properties, essential for fostering a robust and scalable software platform:

- **Loose Coupling:** Each component is implemented with minimal dependencies, ensuring a loosely coupled platform that enhances flexibility and adaptability to evolving requirements.
- **Maintainability and Testability:** Prioritizing high maintainability and testability, our design principles facilitate efficient debugging, updates, and testing of individual components independently.
- **Independently Deployable and Scalable:** Components are designed to be independently deployable whenever possible, allowing for seamless updates and scalability as needed to accommodate varying workloads without compromising overall system integrity.
- **Runtime Configurability:** Emphasizing runtime configurability, our components can adapt dynamically to changing conditions, providing a responsive and versatile operational environment.
- **Extensibility:** The platform is designed to be extensible, enabling the seamless addition of new services, capabilities, and endpoints without necessitating alterations to existing designs and implementations.
- **Model-Driven Framework:** Leveraging a model-driven approach with open interfaces, our platform employs YAML and Open API specifications to capture attributes and supported operations of managed objects, fostering portability and reusability.
- **Communication Mechanisms:** Adopting versatile communication mechanisms capable of implementing publish-subscribe patterns and direct invocations among components.
- **Distributed Architecture:** Embracing a distributed architecture with instances across all domains of the involved parties ensures a resilient and responsive ecosystem.
- **Trusted Data Layer:** Incorporating a distributed trusted data layer, powered by permissioned DLTs, serves as the backbone for identity management, smart-contract-rules automated transactions, and resource discovery.

This comprehensive design framework underscores our commitment to creating a versatile, adaptive, and resilient 6GENABLERS Marketplace, where cutting-edge technologies and principled platform converge to shape the future of collaborative, distributed telecommunications ecosystems.

4.2 Software Platform

From a software perspective, Figure 4-1 provides a comprehensive overview of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace software platform. This figure extends the framework architecture view depicted previously in Figure 3-2 by representing the connection points driving the interactions between the different sub-components. As can be noted, there is a one-to-one mapping that correlates the functional entities defined in the previous section and the software modules to be implemented for the platform prototype. The figure serves as a crucial bridge, aligning the theoretical framework with the practical implementation, thus illuminating the pathways through which the envisioned platform prototype will manifest.

Figure 4-1. 6GENABLERS Marketplace software platform

As illustrated in Figure 4-1, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace platform employs a diverse set of communication mechanisms to facilitate efficient interactions. This platform embraces a hybrid approach, combining direct invocations of REST APIs among components with publish-subscribe patterns. On one front, multiple service endpoints are exposed by various sub-modules, creating a network of interdependencies that contribute to the platform's functionality. This approach extends to the seamless integration with the Network Infrastructure stratum.

Concurrently, the exchange of messages and data flows is predominantly orchestrated through the central Data Bus, positioned as the communication hub interconnecting the myriad modules within the Control and Monitoring Layer. The Data Bus serves as a crucial conduit for real-time information dissemination, facilitating cohesive communication between different components. Notably, the Data Bus services play a pivotal role for the DLT APIs, ensuring the provision of transactional updates, and for the Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC), acting as a means to stay informed about these updates and events from control and monitoring components.

This bidirectional communication extends to critical components such as the Broker Logic for Resource Controller, responsible for reporting resource availability and deployment status. Furthermore, the Data Bus serves as a vital channel for the Proactive SLA Monitoring component, relaying information about the detection and prediction of SLA violations.

4.2.1 Operational Workflows

In this section, we delve into the operational workflows that orchestrate the dynamic functioning of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, by guiding the execution and coordination of various processes within the platform, ensuring seamless interactions among stakeholders and the different sub-components. By elucidating the operational workflows, we aim to provide a nuanced understanding of how the platform implements the main services exposed to the stakeholders.

To illustrate the different services, two stakeholders will be involved in the workflows, namely Stakeholder A, acting as the asset provider (placed to the left and with a blue background) and Stakeholder B, acting as the asset consumer (placed to the right and with an orange background).

4.2.1.1 Offer Creation

Figure 4-2 depicts the different steps involved in the creation of an offer over the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The description of every step is provided next.

This operation is triggered by the Stakeholder acting as the asset provider (i.e. Stakeholder A). To this aim, the Stakeholder A interacts with the Marketplace via the SCSC as the entry-point to drive the SC-ruled transaction flows in the platform and provides the description of the offer to be published (step 1). This request is forwarded to the Offering API for orchestrating various subsequent processes prior to the offer publication (step 2). In this regard, the Offering API initially contacts the Identity Manager API for the actions related to stakeholder identity and permissions verification and to the generation of a DID for the offer (steps 3 and 4). The resulting DID is consequently forwarded back to the Offering API and from there to the SCSC, which is now entitled to let the Stakeholder know that the creation process is in progress (steps 5-7).

Figure 4-2. Workflow for offer creation

In turn, the Offering API interacts with the Smart Discovery Application for the classification of the incoming offer, which results in the assignation of a cluster ID (steps 8-10). Subsequently, the publication of the new offer is announced via the Data Bus, and this message is received by the Broker Logic for Resource Controller, which is listening for this kind of events (steps 11 and 12). This notification triggers the verification of the resource availability at the Network Infrastructure, and the result of such verification is also communicated through the Data Bus, raising the attention of the SCSC, which is following this type of updates (steps 13-15). For the sake of completing the workflow sequence, in this step we assume positive feedback about the resource availability. Nonetheless, other possibilities are also handled accordingly.

After receiving confirmation of the resource availability, the SCSC requests the Offering API for an update of the considered offer (step 16). This request unleashes the process for making this change persistent in the DLT. Specifically, the Offering API sends a registration request to the Trading DLT containing the incoming offer description extended with additional metadata required for internal procedures (e.g. the Cluster ID) (step 17). This results in the propagation of the offer cross-domain through the network of DLT nodes, meaning that this information becomes effective in every other domain thanks to the interconnected network of DLT nodes (step 18).

4.2.1.2 Offers Discovery and Order Creation

Figure 4-3 moves the lens to the other domain, i.e. Stakeholder B, which acts as the asset consumer. This figure illustrates the various steps performed by the 6GENABLERS Marketplace to allow stakeholders the discovery of available offers, and the placement of an order for the individual offer selected by the stakeholder. The description of every step is provided next.

Figure 4-3. Workflow for offers discovery and order creation

In this case, Stakeholder B starts by querying the platform to identify the existing offers that map specific user requirements. To do this, a discovery request is sent to the SCSC with a given intent, containing the expectations of the Stakeholder (step 1). This request is relayed to the Smart Discovery Application for its processing (step 2). Basically, the Smart Discovery Application discerns the received intent and determines the corresponding cluster of offers that responds to the expressed needs (step 3). Using the ID of the identified cluster, the Smart Discovery Application fetches the corresponding offers available at the Trading DLT by requesting them through the Offering API (step 4-6). The returned offers are sent back to the Stakeholder via the SCSC (steps 7 and 8). From this curated list, the Stakeholder selects the most convenient offer and with it composes the payload for creating the order (step 9).

Next, the Stakeholder proceeds with the request for submitting an order for a specific offer via the SCSC (step 10). This request is forwarded to the Order API, for the coordination of actions required for the publication of the order (step 11). Similarly to the offer creation flow, the Order API first reaches the Identity Manager API for verifying the stakeholder identity and permissions and generating a DID for the order (steps 12 and 13). The resulting DID is returned to the Order API and to the SCSC (steps 14 and 15). Then, the Order API proceeds with the submission of the order to the Trading DLT, being it committed and disseminated cross-domain (steps 16 and 17). Finally, the completion of the procedure is exposed to Stakeholder B.

4.2.1.3 Order Deployment

After a successful order placement, Stakeholder B is entitled to request the provision of the acquired telco asset. Figure 4-4 shows the different steps articulated by the platform components for the deployment of an active order over the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This workflow assumes that the provider of the acquired offer is Stakeholder A and illustrates the various actions that are conducted at both domains. The description of every step is provided next.

Figure 4-4. Workflow for order deployment

Initially, Stakeholder B requests the deployment of the order previously created through the SCSC (step 1). With the order DID, the SCSC interacts with the Order API to retrieve the full information of the order from the Trading DLT (steps 2-4). Then, the SCSC compose the SC state object and forwards it to the SC State API, which is introduced in the platform to trigger the deployment of acquired resources and their post-acquisition follow-up (steps 5 and 6). As in the former workflows, the SC State API exchange the information related to the requesting stakeholder with the Identity Manager API for verifying its identity and permissions and obtaining a DID for the SC State (steps 7 and 8). The resulting DID is then returned to the SC State API and from there to the SCSC, which is able now to indicate to the Stakeholder that the deployment is in progress (steps 9-11).

Next, the SC State API proceeds with the publishing of the SC State on the Trading DLT, for its cross-domain dissemination (steps 12 and 13). Once this propagation is performed, the SC State becomes available also at the provider domain, where the SC State API retrieves it and notifies of its existence to the other components in the domain that are listening to the Data Bus (steps 14 and 15). Such is the case of the Broker Logic for Resource Controller, which first revises the availability of the resource to be provisioned (steps 16-18). After confirming the availability, this module sends the instantiation request to the network manager or orchestration entity in charge of conducting the deployment (step 19). Once the deployment is completed, this result is also notified in the Data Bus and from there read by the SCSC (steps 20 and 21).

Then, the SCSC contacts the SC State API for updating the ledger record in the Trading DLT of the handled SC state to reflect its latest achieved status (i.e. deployed) (steps 22 and 23). Consequently, this status update is propagated also to the consumer's domain via communication over the DLT network (step 24). After being committed to the ledger, this information becomes available for consultation by Stakeholder B. This is achieved

by following the conceived sequence of interactions that involves the SCSC, the SC State API and the Trading DLT (steps 25-29).

While this workflow describes the steps for the deployment of an order, the aspects related to SLA are left outside since a dedicated workflow for it is going to be described in the upcoming subsection.

4.2.1.4 SLA Compliance Tracking

The procedure described with the former workflow is extended now in Figure 4-5, which focuses on illustrating the steps involved in the follow up of the SLA compliance. For the sake of completeness, this workflow assumes the occurrence of an SLA violation and illustrates the various actions that are conducted at both domains in order to notify the stakeholders involved and record the incident in the ledger. The description of every step is provided next.

Figure 4-5. Workflow for SLA compliance tracking

This workflow continues after the Broker Logic for Resource Controller at the provider domain notifies into the Data Bus that the deployment has been completed successfully and, in this message, also the SLA terms are included. The SLA terms indicate the agreed objectives, including the considered metrics and its target values. This information is fundamental for the Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator and the Proactive SLA Monitoring.

In particular, after retrieving the SLA terms, the Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator starts the process of collecting the corresponding metrics from the network infrastructure, which are subsequently inserted into the Data Lake (steps 2-4). In parallel, the Proactive SLA Monitoring also gathers the SLA terms and consumes the monitored metrics that have been pushed to the Data Lake in order to compare collected metrics against the established SLA rules (steps 5-7). Assuming the performed evaluation detects an SLA violation, this is immediately communicated to the Data Bus, from where the SCSC retrieves this information (steps 8 and 9).

Next, the SCSC forwards this information both internally to the SC State API (step 10) and externally to the provider stakeholder (step 11). In turn, the SC State API sends this violation in the form of update request to the Trading DLT, from where it is disseminated to the other domain (steps 12 and 13).

Then, at the consumer's domain, the update of the SC state is retrieved by the SC State API, which publishes it in the Data Lake (steps 14 and 15). Finally, the SCSC retrieves

the message published in the Data Lake and notifies the event to the stakeholder (steps 16 and 17).

5 Conclusion

This document unveils a comprehensive architecture for the transformative landscape of the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace envisioned within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. Delving into the intricate technical facets and functionalities of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, this document serves as a guiding beacon for stakeholders, developers, and architects engaged in the realization of this groundbreaking initiative.

In the dynamic landscape of 6G environments, where network infrastructures need to be flexible, provisioned on-demand, and capable of providing pervasive computing and connectivity, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace positions as a promising enabler. The 6GENABLERS Marketplace represents a holistic solution that adeptly addresses the pivotal requirements for the evolution of 6G networks, namely sustainability, ubiquity, and trustworthiness. This innovative platform has been strategically designed to align with the sustainability goals of the telecommunications industry while ensuring widespread accessibility and fostering a high degree of trust among stakeholders.

The framework architecture of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is underpinned by four core functional systems, DLT, Smart Contract, Smart Discovery, and SLA assurance, each playing a pivotal role in shaping the collaborative and innovative landscape of the platform. These functional systems are designed to synergistically interact, providing a seamless and efficient environment for participants.

The architecture outlined in this deliverable not only sets the foundation for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project but also embodies a pivotal enabler for stakeholders to collectively harness resources, heralding a new era of technological advancements. Through adherence to best practices and meticulous planning, the architecture presented here aims to propel the telecommunications industry into a realm characterized by heightened efficiency, transparency, and innovation.

The platform's ability to facilitate the creation and showcasing of offers signifies a pivotal milestone. Stakeholders can now effortlessly trade their resources and services within the collaborative ecosystem, streamlining the process of connecting with potential consumers. This functionality not only enhances accessibility but also contributes to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the Marketplace.

In conclusion, the Architecture for DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace lays the groundwork for a paradigm shift in the telecommunications landscape. With a focus on multi-party collaboration in dynamic 6G environments, this deliverable positions the 6GENABLERS-DLT project at the forefront of innovation, setting the stage for the development of a platform that transcends traditional boundaries, fostering transparency, efficiency, and collaborative excellence in the evolving 6G ecosystem.

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